

Gamifying Education: Exploring the Power of Game-Based Learning

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Publication Date: 2025/02/19

Abstract: This study is about how using games can help students learn better. The world of education needs new and exciting ways to teach, and this research looks into how games can make learning more fun and effective. The power of game-based learning has been highlighted and clearly demonstrated in this research paper. The aim is to build trust in game based learning and promote its use in classroom set up. Here, data was collected by online surveys using Google Forms which was filled by students, teachers, and parents, case studies, and a review of existing papers on same topic. Survey outcomes confirmed that game-based learning significantly boosts student engagement by making learning enjoyable, interactive and efficient in delivering practical knowledge. By combining gamification with traditional teaching, educators can create a best learning experience that benefits students in multiple ways.

How to Cite: Arnav Deore; Saniya Bohra; Pratima Bhalekar. (2025). Gamifying Education: Exploring the Power of Game-Based Learning. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, 10(1), 2669-2676. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14891745>.

I. INTRODUCTION

In today's generation, where things are changing rapidly, so traditional way of teaching are struggling to meet students need and expectations. As technology and digital resources such as Gamification, online content, social media become more popular, teachers are searching for new ways not only to just maintain students interest but also to make learning more effective.

So, game theory is a branch of mathematics that studies how people make decisions in situation where the outcome are dependent on the action of another people. Game-based learning is a new approach. It uses games to make learning more interactive, effective and fun. It gains students attention and helps to understand concepts more clearly. By merging gamification with lessons, learning becomes more enjoyable and fun. It is a creative and unique way to teach which makes learning engaging and effective. It encourages students to honoraly participate instead of just listening to lectures, answering questions etc. Here by gamification, student engage in problem solving, making decision etc. Overall it is a powerful and strong way of teaching where students spend maximum of their time in vital world as compared to real world. By combining games and education, learning becomes more fun and entertaining for all ages.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

In this paper we can see according to Gagne an instructional plan can generate both appropriate environmental stimuli and instructional interaction and thereby bringing about change in the cognitive structure and

operational of a learner.[1] This paper introduces a framework for using game theory tournaments as a base to impliment competition based learning.[2] This paper aims to create effective algorithm and model to analysis various game senario and predict optimal decision for players.[4] In this paper we can identify that game theory provide model of situations in whichever chosen action can give us indifferent cases, results with a probability the aim is to find the optimal mix strsyer for the professors to ensure best possible result in teaching. [5]. This paper objective is to evolve a composite optimum strategy for faculty member in order to achieve the best possible results for any fragmented group of students.[7]This paper has shown the effect of game and simulation with regard to achieving specific learning objectives, the researcher identified three learning outcomes when integrating games into learning process : cognitive behavioural and effective.[8] This chapter demonstrate how game theory can be used as tool to both develop and manage students engagement in higher education. [9] In This paper student use educational application 'pagamo' to study the motor learning and development course. The top three motives to play pa-gamo were fun, self learning and want to get higher grade in final examination.[10] This study proposed a game model for collaborative learning that aim to analyse dynamic process by which bounded rational students adapt their strategy in Collabrative learning.[11] In this article discuss both long standing connection between game theory as well as new connection streaming from emerging application. [12] This paper describes two active learning activities which aim to introduce to the game theoretic concept of best response dynamics and repeated game analytics. [13] This article first elebrates the

theory of game and then analyses the influence of game theory development of maths literacy education.[14]

III. METHODOLOGY

This study uses quantitative research technique to identify effectiveness and acceptance of game based learning in education. The aim is to understand and increase students awareness towards game based learning as compared to traditional methods. To collect and analyse data we have used questionnaire method created through google form, our goal was to collect huge amount of responses i.e data, so that we can reveal and find the insights of the term game based learning.

The participants for this questionnaire were selected from students aged 18-24. This age range was selected because they were most likely to engage with the benefit from game based learning techniques. If the participants are divides on gender basis, there were an equal number of respondants of male and female although male respondants were higher but overall both we equal. This questionnaire was also filled by teaching professionals who offered their valuable feedback based on their experience and observations in improving education with gamification.

Data was collected in a systematic manner using a step by step structured questionnaire created via Google form. The questionnaire included a total of 22 question divided into multiple section and types. It was mainly divides into 5 sections.

- Personal Information
- Activity
- Teaching Methodologing
- Awareness and need of gamification
- Case Studies

Here in there different sections, most of the questions were Multiple-choice question (MCQs) which were used to collect quantitative data regarding participants opinons and what they think about game-based learning.

An activity was conducted using a interative element within the questionnaire in order to identify how participant engaged in filling the form. Questionnaire was prepared in such a way that single question was repeated multiple times to identify weather the user is fully engaged in form or not.

At the end, participants were provided a case study with real world example to know their practical knowledge and their thinking in different situations. This forced students to think critically to give best answer for the situation. Parents/Gurdians also provided their views on how gamification would affect the academic growth of their children.

This questionnaire was distributed on Social media which was easily accessible by participants. All the responses which are collected and stored were gathered anonymously.

Fig 1: Distribution of Age

Maximum of the participants age was around 18-24yrs old which was the correct age range where gamification will help.

Fig 2: Traditional Teaching Meeting Expectations

As per maximum participants, they feel, there is some thing lacking in traditional ways of learning and for this reason, it doesn't meet their expectations

Fig 3: Disadvantages of Current Education

According to 58% of participants, current education system contains lack of practicality which can be solved by gamification.

Fig 4: Motivation for Playing Games

According to this survey, 66% people play games for entertainment purposes, if game theory would be applied, candidates would engage more in gaming if it educates them.

Fig 5: Awareness of Game-Based Learning

Most of the candidates who have participated are familiar with gamification.

Fig 6: Application of Gamification

Many of the participants have used the educational application hence if such applications are developed with proper analysis and technique, it would definitely upskill students.

Fig 7: Views of Gamification

83% of candidates think that gamification can lead to upskilling themselves, the only challenge is to develop a perfect platform which focuses on learning via playing.

Fig 8: Comparison of Both

As in traditional way of learning delivering practical knowledge is tough and gamification can solve this problem, 67% candidates think the same.

Fig 9: Where Should Gamification be Applied

Gamification can be applied for all educational stage, the only thing is to be done is increasing level of complexity as per stage.

Fig 10: Subject Under Gamification

41% of candidates think Maths can be made more interesting using gamification as well as Programming subjects and business.

Fig 11: Final Conclusion

Maximum participants feel that, gamification can upskill students in academics and is good choice over all others ways to learning.

Fig. 12: Case Study

In this case study, we have described 2 situations from which candidates have selected one option according to the situation.

IV. CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates the potential of game theory and gamification to revolutionize the educational process by making learning more engaging, interactive, and effective. Traditional methods often fail to fully address the diverse needs and interests of modern students, but game-based learning presents an innovative solution. It also highlights how combining games with education can create a better learning experience for students of all ages. Gamification encourages active participation, critical thinking, and collaboration, making it a strong and effective teaching method for the future. As education continues to evolve, game-based learning can bridge the gap between traditional teaching and modern student needs, ensuring better outcomes for everyone involved.

The research also focuses on understanding students' awareness of gamification, as well as collecting feedback from students, teachers, and parents on how game-based learning can benefit academic growth. By combining the insights gained from the study with game theory principles, this research offers a framework for educators to create more inclusive and effective teaching methods.

Since Game-based learning is helpful and useful, but it shouldn't completely replace traditional learning methods. It should be used alongside them to make learning better and easier to understand.

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